

Collision Avoidance for Autonomous Underwater Vehicles

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Abstract—The areas of application for autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs) are diverse and are not limited to exploring areas. One additional area of application is the extraction of raw materials for electric-car batteries. This involves gently extracting polymetallic nodules from the seabed so that the seabed is not damaged. For such an AUV deployment, the route must be planned. Planned missions can be simulated in advance to test mechanisms that help the AUV to detect, fix, and also avoid problems. However, there may be unplanned obstacles or ocean currents on the route that the AUV has to avoid, which causes the AUV to deviate from its planned mission. To this end, this paper uses and extends simulation models for the movement of an AUV such that we can simulate its mission while it is enabled to autonomously deviate from its route to avoid obstacles. Using case studies, we demonstrate in the OMNeT++ simulator that our developed simulation model allows for both planned missions of an AUV and response to unplanned obstacles.

Index Terms—AUV, collision avoidance, simulation

I. INTRODUCTION

Our earth has a surface area of 510 million square kilometers, of which 29 percent is land mass. This means 71 percent of the earth's surface is covered with water. Although most of the earth is covered by water, only a small part of it has been fully explored. Especially under water, there are many unknown regions. This is partly because these areas are located in environments that are hostile to humans. For instance, there are underwater environments beneath meter-thick layers of ice, as is the case at the poles, or the areas that are so deep that the pressure there becomes so high that humans could not survive there for long, if at all [1].

Various solutions have been developed for these cases, one of which is autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs). These are unmanned small submarines that navigate independently. Through AUVs, there is now the ability to penetrate areas where humans would not otherwise survive. However, the missions must be carefully planned because the environment in these regions also poses a threat to the AUVs. There is a variety of unknown hazards in these regions that will result in high costs if the AUV is damaged by them. In order to test and optimize planned missions for their feasibility, simulations with suitable motion models are indispensable. In addition, it is necessary for the simulation to react autonomously to environmental influences such as obstacles or ocean currents.

A variety of problems can occur during an underwater mission. One problem may be that an unknown object is on the route of the AUV. In this case, the AUV must be able to react to it, i.e., avoid a collision. Mechanisms for collision avoidance when an AUV is moving are the main goal of our work. We simulate the mechanisms using the OMNeT++ simulation environment and the OMNeT++ framework INET [2], [3]. Several steps are performed in the simulation. In the first step, the AUV travels a planned mission route. The next step is for the AUV to detect and react to obstacles while following its planned route. The AUV is able to perform an evasive motion to avoid the obstacle. For the evasive movement, the AUV must detect the obstacles themselves. As the objects are detected, various data about the object are collected so that the AUV can obtain an image of the object as accurately as possible. This data includes rough coordinates that describe where the obstacle is approximately located. This data is processed to calculate the most favorable route. To do this, the most favorable route must be determined using rules sufficient to make an informed decision. In summary, the contribution of this paper is to use and extend the simulation models for motion in INET so that the AUV can follow a planned mission and detect and avoid obstacles on its planned route.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. First, we look at related work in Section II. In Section III, we introduce the concept for our simulation model. The concept includes mechanisms for detecting and avoiding differently shaped objects. Section IV describes how the concept is implemented in OMNeT++ and INET and shows an evaluation with the help of two case studies. The paper is concluded in Section V.

II. RELATED WORK

As already described, the areas of application for an AUV are very diverse and more and more AUVs are also being used. As a result, there is a variety of different projects and applications for each type of AUV. In the following, we will take a closer look at a few solutions that deal with a topic similar to the topic of investigation in this paper. In addition, projects that specifically address individual aspects or even the entire AUV are mentioned.

There are a lot of projects that are carried out in Germany as well as in other parts of the world. One institute that deals

with AUVs but also with autonomous vehicles in general is the German Aerospace Center (Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt, DLR). The DLR is working on a variety of projects that deal with maritime issues. One project, for example, is the Marlin project, which is about the protection of maritime facilities as an example offshore wind farms. This project deals with developing a new type of situational awareness system, for monitoring maritime infrastructures in realtime [4]. Until now, only systems for monitoring from a distance were used, but with this system, monitoring from close range becomes possible. Among other things, the system will be used with AUVs to closely examine maritime infrastructure.

Another major project is being run by the Laboratório de Sistemas e Tecnologia Subaquática (LSTS). The institute deals specifically with underwater systems. In doing so, numerous systems has been developed in a variety of projects, one of which is DUNE. This is an on-board system that is responsible for every kind of action in a system, i.e., every action with the sensors and the actuators, as well as all the communication, navigation, control and execution of missions [5]. In principle, the system is a completely separate operating system for AUVs and other drones. Everything that is needed for the operation of an AUV was defined there and it is still being expanded and improved. Regarding the topic under investigation in the paper, there is a separate section in DUNE for evasion, which deals with any kind of maneuvers and more specifically also the evasion of obstacles. The LSTS also deals generally with individual aspects around maritime systems, be it the more precise planning of missions and generally the refinement of movements and optimization of these. This also includes the planning of a route. Known possible obstacles will be taken into account right from the beginning.

Other papers deal with these aspects as well. One paper specifically deals with route optimization using high-resolution ocean models [6]. This involves the acceleration and speed of the AUV, which are optimized by means of more accurate ocean models, since this allows currents or other environmental influences to be considered when planning the route.

Also, there is a variety of solutions, each using their own programs as well as relying on existing ones. In another work a complete system for an AUV was built, starting with the mission planning up to the implementation of the mission in the AUV, as well as also the function to avoid obstacles [7]. There, the complete in-house development of a module for the control of the AUV was made. The environment as well as the bottom of the sea are completely simulated so that the aspects of the environment can be taken into account.

In summary, it can be concluded that there are very many different solutions that are still being further developed today. There were differences in the implementation of the individual projects in particular, because these are systems that are specially tailored to the application and are being further developed in terms of very specific optimizations.

III. CONCEPT FOR COLLISION AVOIDANCE

In this section, the concept for collision avoidance is described. The AUV has to act autonomously, i.e., it has to be

Fig. 1. Modular architecture of the AUV.

able to react to different situations and finds a way to avoid problems. For this to be possible, a mechanism must exist that takes into account different collision avoidance situations that the AUV may encounter. To avoid an obstacle, the AUV takes the most favorable avoidance path, deviating from the originally planned mission route.

BonnMotionMobility, which is included in INET, was chosen as the model for the motion of an AUV because it is a route-based model. In route-based motion models, previously defined routes are transferred to OMNeT++ by file and then processed step by step. These files are created via external software. BonnMotionMobility allows the representation of a three-dimensional space, as well as a three-dimensional movement. This is necessary to allow swerving in multiple directions. Speed and orientation are variable.

In order to enable an evasive maneuver, several aspects must be considered. First, the AUV must be able to detect an obstacle. Once the obstacle has been detected, logic must be used to calculate which path the AUV takes to avoid the obstacle. The last step is about the avoidance itself, i.e., which maneuver the AUV has to perform to safely pass the obstacle.

The architecture of the AUV simulation model is modularly divided into three modules, as shown in Figure 1. As shown in Figure 1, the AUV is moving towards an obstacle. It notices that there is an obstacle in front of it and avoids it after deciding for a path, which can be seen from the red and green arrows. The entire avoidance process takes place in the three different modules, as can be seen in Figure 1 when zooming into the AUV. The two main modules are used for navigation and evasive maneuvers. The third module is a submodule within the navigation module. In what follows, we will describe each of these three modules in detail.

A. Navigation Module

As already mentioned above, the detection of the obstacle as well as the initial processing and transmission of the data

Fig. 2. Architecture of the navigation module.

takes place in the navigation module. In addition, the general navigation of the AUV is also located here. Let us have a look at the actual concept of the navigation module, i.e., which data enters the module, how it is processed, and which data leaves the module. For this, we will look again at which aspects are important for the evasion and how exactly the navigation module is involved. The navigation module takes over especially the part with the recognition of the obstacle, i.e., the general recognition but also the recording of data from the obstacle and forwarding it correctly.

The architecture of the navigation module is depicted in Figure 2. At the beginning of the entire maneuver, the AUV travels on its normal mission route, then detects via sensors that there is an obstacle in front of it. As soon as this happens, a signal is sent indicating that there is an obstacle in front of the AUV. In addition, information from the obstacle is collected at the same time such as the absolute coordinates of the sides of the obstacle, i.e., the points on the height of the AUV, which are located at the left and right end of the obstacle and the corresponding orientation whether the point is on the left or on the right of the AUV. This data is then transferred to the navigation module. The data of the obstacle is then directly passed on to the logic submodule which is located within the navigation module.

Upon reception of the signal, a sequence of actions in the navigation module is triggered. As soon as the signal is present, the mission route has to be left and the AUV needs to calculate an alternative route. For this purpose, corresponding scenarios are defined within the navigation module, so that it is possible to react to different situations. For instance, the obstacle might be located on the path in front of the AUV. The navigation module signals the logic submodule to perform the necessary calculations and to take a decision in which direction to swerve. After the data has been processed in the

logic submodule, the logic submodule passes this data, as well as a decision about the direction of the avoidance, back to the navigation module. This data is then passed on to the collision-avoidance module.

In principle, the navigation module serves as a kind of distributor. This is because all the data first goes in there and the navigation module then distributes it to the right modules. This is solved as described by different scenarios, which are self-defined beforehand. This way, the navigation module can easily be extended in a modular way by defining new scenarios which then control other modules.

B. Logic Module

With the help of the navigation module, the AUV can detect obstacles and record required information about the obstacle. The obstacle data to signal that there is an obstacle in front of the AUV is transmitted to the logic submodule. Let us have a look at the actual maneuver of an evasion. Once the AUV has recognized that there is an obstacle in front of it, it concludes that it has to leave its actual mission route and avoid the obstacle. The question is in which way it will avoid the obstacle, i.e., which route it will take to avoid it. There are a lot of possible routes to avoid the obstacle and in principle there are even virtually infinite ways. In the best case the AUV decides for the most favorable way, for example, the way that causes the AUV to consume the least energy, the way that is the fastest, or the way that is the shortest. Currently, the most favorable path is configured as the path on which the absolute distance of the AUV to one of the two outermost points of the obstacle, which the AUV can detect, is the smallest.

For the determination of the path, the logic submodule needs two kinds of data. Firstly, the signal from the sensors is required so that the logic submodule knows that there is an obstacle in front of the AUV. Secondly, it needs the information that the AUV could capture from the obstacle, specifically the absolute coordinates of the outermost sides of the obstacle that the AUV can see as well as the orientation of these coordinates, i.e. whether they are to the right or left of the AUV. Once this data arrives at the logic submodule, it can start working. In order to explain the individual steps in the module, Figure 3 is used. As shown in Figure 3, the required data is transferred from the navigation module to the logic submodule. When the data arrives at the logic submodule, it starts to perform the necessary calculations to make a decision on which path to take to avoid the obstacle. In the first step, the logic submodule has to retrieve additional data that it needs to take an informed decision. This includes the current position of the AUV, since this is needed to calculate the absolute distance to the respective outermost edges of the obstacle. To calculate the absolute distance, the first step is to calculate the vectors from the current position of the AUV to the outermost visible edges of the obstacle. Once this is done, the magnitude of these vectors is calculated. This value is then taken as the absolute distance, and is used to take a decision about the direction in which the obstacle will be avoided.

This decision is taken with the help of defined rules. In principle, the rules are used to decide which absolute value

Fig. 3. Architecture of the logic module.

Fig. 5. Architecture of the collision-avoidance module.

Rules	$ABS1 > ABS2$	$ABS1 < ABS2$	$ABS1 = ABS2$
Orientation ABS1 left and ABS2 right	Right	Left	Right
Orientation ABS1 right and ABS2 links	Left	Right	Right

ABS1 = Absolute value 1 ABS2 = Absolute Value 2

Fig. 4. Simplified representation of the rules.

of the vectors is smaller, i.e., at first glance the shorter path. However, it is also important that the respective orientation of the edges of the obstacle is considered, because the AUV must also know in which direction the shorter vector points, so that it also draws the correct conclusion from the rules. As apparent from Figure 4, the rules always refer to the ratio of the absolute values of the vectors and depending on the orientation of the edges, the decision is taken whether to go right or left. When a final decision is taken, it is saved and then as a last step the distance between the AUV and the obstacle is determined. For this purpose, a safety distance is defined, which consists of the absolute value of the vector of the side where the obstacle is to be avoided and a fixed value, which can be defined by the user. This safety distance is then passed with the decision of the direction first to the navigation module which then passes this data further to the collision-avoidance module to be described in the following.

C. Collision-Avoidance Module

With the help of the logic submodule, the AUV is able to detect an obstacle, process the data of the obstacle, and use this data to take an informed decision in which direction the avoidance maneuver goes. In this subsection, we describe the movement as most important part of the evasive maneuver itself. As mentioned above, there are virtually infinite ways for the evasive maneuver and so far only the direction in which the maneuver goes was determined. Now, we describe how the movement looks like, how the AUV will leave the actual route, how the AUV will keep the safety distance, and how it returns to the mission route in the end. First, we take a look at the chosen motion model again, which is BonnMotionMobility. One advantage of BonnMotionMobility is that it is a route-based model which means that a prescribed route is followed. This is used to give the AUV a new route for collision avoidance by providing the AUV a new coordinate for the avoidance route. In order to explain how this process works exactly, Figure 5 is described in the following. At the beginning, the collision-avoidance module receives all the data it needs from the navigation module. This data contains the decision in which direction the avoidance maneuver goes and the avoidance module also receives the required data about the obstacle as well as the previously defined safety distance. As soon as this data has been recorded by the avoidance module, the avoidance module evaluates the decision on the avoidance direction and determines the direction for the further calculation. In the next step, the calculation of the avoidance route begins. For this purpose, the vector of the current position to the original destination is calculated first, i.e., where the obstacle is currently located. When this is done, the final avoidance distance is calculated, which is composed of the absolute value of the vector to the original target and the safety distance.

The distance is then used to calculate the coordinate for

Fig. 6. Representation of a simple maneuver.

Fig. 7. Representation of an advanced maneuver.

the collision-avoidance step. In this calculation, it is generally true that a vector to this coordinate that serves as the point for the avoidance step is approximately at 90° to the vector to the original target, i.e., it is nearly perpendicular to this vector. After the evasion coordinate has been calculated, this coordinate is passed to the AUV and the AUV then performs a move to this point. When the point has been reached, the AUV tries to return to the original route. However, it is possible that the obstacle is still next to the AUV, so that it is still in the path of the AUV. As soon as this happens, the sensors of the AUV will detect it and the AUV will send a signal again. However, in this case no completely new calculation is needed for a new decision in which direction to swerve. The data is passed to the logic submodule so that the data is changed and the avoidance module knows that it needs to make a different move. Then, the avoidance module uses the avoidance distance for the calculation like in the the first avoidance step.

Another coordinate is then calculated for the additional collision-avoidance step. This coordinate has a similar position as the first coordinate but it is only shifted in the direction of the mission direction. Thus, in principle the AUV drives a route straight ahead parallel to the obstacle, which corresponds to the length of the avoidance distance. This new coordinate is then passed back to the AUV. The AUV executes the movement again, returns to the original route, and completes its actual mission again. The case that the obstacle is still next to or in front of the AUV can theoretically occur several times. Therefore, the signal can be triggered several times and each time the same calculation is executed. This procedure can run until the AUV is able to safely return to its original route.

From these possibilities of coordinate calculations, different kinds of evasive maneuvers result. Two of them are shown in the Figures 6 and 7. As can be seen in Figure 6, after detecting an obstacle, the AUV performs a movement towards a point that is nearly perpendicular to the original route. After reaching this point, the AUV returns to the origin route. Since one step was sufficient to avoid the obstacle, the AUV can safely return to the original route without another evasive step. Again, in Figure 7 one can see that one single evasive step was not sufficient and therefore another step had to be executed. When returning to the original route for the first time, the obstacle is still in the way of the AUV. This leads to a further step, so that the AUV moves a further distance parallel to the obstacle and then returns to the original route. The entire evasive maneuver is then completed. The obstacle is avoided and the mission can continue.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION AND EVALUATION

This section deals with the implementation and evaluation.

A. Implementation

First, we address how the concept was implemented. The concept was implemented in OMNeT++ version 6, and the INET framework version 4.2 was used for the motion simulation. In OMNeT++, the structure is such that there are two ned files where the network was defined. There is also an ini file where the motion model and properties of the environment and the AUV have been defined. The functions themselves are defined in a C++ file; for the sake of clarity, the functions and also variables were mostly defined in a header file.

B. Evaluation

Finally, the implemented simulation model was evaluated. This verifies whether the implementation of the concept works. To check this, case studies were conducted and then examined to see if the expected result matched the actual result. Two case studies were defined. A mission route was predefined for both case studies. The route is an undulating pattern on which the AUV repeatedly moves back and forth (see Figure 8). For the case studies, objects are needed on the route or next to the route. To insert the objects, an XML file was used in OMNeT++. There, the objects are defined by coordinates and their dimensions. The case studies run in such a way that the AUV travels the mission route and at a predefined time an object appears in front of the AUV. The case studies include a maximum of two obstacles and the widest part of the obstacle is at the front of the object that the AUV can see directly.

In the first case study, the most general case is assumed to verify the basic functionalities. The simplest case is a scenario where only one object is on the mission route of the AUV. In this scenario, after detecting the obstacle, the AUV starts calculating a route to avoid it. For this purpose, the object was defined and placed to pass the obstacle on the left from the AUV's point of view. In doing so, the AUV leaves its origin route at a nearly 90° angle. As soon as the new point for avoidance is reached, the AUV returns to the original route. Hence, the AUV comes too close to the obstacle again, so that another avoidance step is required. After this step has also been completed, the AUV returns to the original route. The AUV choses the right route, i.e., the route on which the distance to the outermost corner of the AUV is the smallest. Furthermore, the evasive movement looks similar to Figure 7. A screenshot of this maneuver is considered and evaluated (see

Fig. 8. Planned mission route of the AUV.

Fig. 9. Screenshot of a standard maneuver from OMNeT++.

Figure 9). Figure 9 shows how the evasive maneuver looks like in OMNeT++. In the figure, the AUV has approached the obstacle from above. The obstacle in the case is a gray cuboid. This obstacle was detected and a route was calculated which led the AUV past the obstacle on the left side from the view of the AUV. In addition, it can also be seen that when returning to the original route, the AUV came too close to the obstacle and therefore had to perform another evasive step.

The second case study represents a more complex case with multiple objects in the field of view of the AUV. In this scenario, there is also an object on the mission route in front of the AUV, but there is another object directly adjacent to the object on the route. The object is so close to the other object that it would be in the way of the AUV if it swerved in that direction. The AUV will again approach the obstacle in the same way and detect it. In addition, it also recognizes that there is another object on one side. When the AUV has calculated a new route, it should have decided for the route that passes the obstacle on the left from the AUV's point of view. It should come to this decision because the obstacle on the route is the same as in the first case study. However, the AUV then realizes that the second object is located exactly on that side and therefore it cannot pass the obstacle on the left. Otherwise, it would collide with the second obstacle or it would have to take another route, which would cost more energy and time. Consequently, the AUV decides to take the route that passes the obstacle on the right. The maneuver itself looks similar to the first case study and Figure 7. A screenshot

Fig. 10. Screenshot of a maneuver with two objects from OMNeT++.

of this maneuver is considered and evaluated (see Figure 10). In Figure 10, one can see how the evasive maneuver looks like in OMNeT++. The AUV approaches the obstacle from above, which in this case is a gray cuboid. The obstacle is detected and the calculation of the avoidance route takes place. Since it is the same obstacle as in the first case study, it should decide for a route that passes the obstacle on the left. However, the AUV recognizes that there is another object there and hence decides for the actually longer route that passes the obstacle on the right side. If the shape of the maneuver is compared with the shape from Figure 7, it can be seen that they look similar and the maneuver is executed correctly. In both case studies, the AUV performs the evasive maneuvers as expected.

V. CONCLUSION

The contribution of this paper was to extend a simulation model for motion in the OMNeT++ framework INET so that an AUV can detect and avoid differently shaped obstacles. For this purpose, a concept for a modular architecture was developed and implemented. Several mechanisms were implemented in the concept. One of them is obstacle detection. The AUV detects if there is an obstacle in front of it and can then process data from that obstacle. A logic then decides which direction it should take to avoid the obstacle. Safety distances and the rough shape of the obstacle are taken into account. In case studies, we have shown that our simulation model works correctly and an AUV is able to detect and avoid obstacles.

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